

A NEW RECORD OF *EURYOMMA PEREGRINUM* (MEIGEN, 1826) (DIPTERA: FANNIIDAE) FROM THE AFROTROPICAL REGION

NOWE STANOWISKO *EURYOMMA PEREGRINUM* (MEIGEN, 1826) (DIPTERA: FANNIIDAE) Z KRAINY ETIOPSKIEJ

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ABSTRACT. *Euryomma* STEIN, 1899 is the second largest genus within the family Fanniidae (Diptera). The genus comprises some 16 species with a predominantly New World distribution. The species of *Euryomma* are associated with synanthropic or forest areas and some of them may occur on decomposed matter of vegetable or animal origin. Nonetheless, the biology of these flies is poorly known. *Euryomma peregrinum* (MEIGEN, 1826) is the only cosmopolitan representative of the genus. The species became widely dispersed through commerce. *Euryomma peregrinum* was thought to occur sporadically in the Afrotropical region, but extensive literature search revealed no official records of the occurrence of this species in mainland Africa. This paper provides the first record of *E. peregrinum* from Namibia in continental Africa.

KEYWORDS: Fanniidae, *Euryomma peregrinum*, Afrotropical Region, Africa, new record

INTRODUCTION

Fanniidae (Diptera) are a relatively small group of flies with over 360 described species (DOMÍNGUEZ & PONT 2014). The Fanniidae family is divided into 5 genera: *Australofannia* PONT, 1977, *Euryomma* STEIN, 1899, *Fannia* ROBINEAU-DESVOIDY, 1830, *Piezura* RONDANI, 1866 and *Zealandofannia* DOMÍNGUEZ & PONT, 2014. The most species-rich, cosmopolitan genus *Fannia* is known for its relationship with man (CARVALHO *et al.* 2003). Some fanniids are of great hygienic and medical importance (BENECKE 1998; BENECKE *et al.* 2004; BENECKE & LESSIG 2001) e.g., *Fannia canicularis* (LINNAEUS, 1761) and *Fannia scalaris* (FABRICIUS, 1794) may cause myiasis in humans and animals (CHILLCOTT 1961; ZUMPT

1965). Several species that have been noted on human corpses (CARVALHO *et al.* 2000) are used as medico-legal indicators, especially for estimating mPMI (minimum post-mortem interval) (AMENDT *et al.* 2011): *F. canicularis*, *F. scalaris*, *F. manicata* (MEIGEN, 1826), *F. leucosticta* (MEIGEN, 1838) (VELÁSQUEZ *et al.* 2013) and *F. pusio* (WIEDEMANN, 1830) (VASCONCELOS *et al.* 2017).

Most often adult Fanniidae are found in forests, less often in open areas. Males usually form swarms under tree branches or above forest paths, while for females, decomposing organic matter of all kinds is attractive (CARVALHO *et al.* 2003; ROZKOŠNÝ *et al.* 1997). Larvae are saprophages and occur in decaying organic matter of plant and animal origin. Some of them develop in dead fungi, bird nests (ADAMSKA *et al.* 2018) and other insect nests, mammal burrows and bat roosts (FERRAR 1987; LYNEBORG 1970; ROZKOŠNÝ *et al.* 1997). The range of occurrence of the Fanniidae family is referred to as worldwide (DOMÍNGUEZ & PONT 2014). They are present primarily in the Holarctic; relatively numerous species diversity has been reported in the Neotropical, Australian and Oriental Region, and much less in the Afrotropical Region (PONT 1991).

Euryomma is the second largest genus of the family Fanniidae that contains some 16 species (DOMÍNGUEZ & ROIG-JUÑENT 2017). The vast majority of species have a predominantly New World range of distribution. *Euryomma peregrinum* (MEIGEN, 1826) is the only cosmopolitan representative of the genus and the species has become widely dispersed through commerce. To Europe, *E. peregrinum* was probably introduced from the Neotropical region (ROZKOŠNÝ *et al.* 1997). According to GRISALES (2016) *Euryomma* can be distinguished from other fanniids by the presence of such features as: vein A₂ slightly curved and first presutural dorsocentral setae less than half the length of second. *Euryomma*, similarly to about 30 other species of Fanniidae family (GRZYWACZ *et al.* 2017) has repeatedly been noted on human corpses and animal cadavers (ABALLAY *et al.* 2012). Nevertheless, the usefulness of these species for medico-legal purposes, particularly mPMI estimations, requires more detailed studies (ABALLAY *et al.* 2012; GRZYWACZ *et al.* 2017).

Euryomma peregrinum was thought to occur sporadically in the Afrotropical region. Extensive literature search revealed no official records of the occurrence of this species in mainland Africa, either in Palearctic or Afrotropical part of the continent. The aim of this paper is to report new records of *Euryomma peregrinum* from the Afrotropical Region and especially from mainland Africa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The examined material was obtained during a two-week visit to Namibia as a part of the 9th International Congress of Dipterology in Windhoek. While the expedition, weekly research field was conducted at the Gobabeb Research & Training Centre (Namib-Naukluft National Park). The material was collected in Walvis Bay, nearby Bird Sanctuary (22°58'01"S 14°31'56"E), using an entomological net. The area is sandy marshes surrounded by a desert (FIG. 1). The material has been properly prepared on an entomological pin and labelled. Sample identification was performed using the key of ROZKOŠNÝ *et al.* (1997). Material identification was verified based on the collection of the Natural History Museum, London, UK (NHM). The originally collected material was deposited in the collections of the Department of Ecology and Biogeography, Nicolaus Copernicus University (Toruń, Poland).

FIG.1. Walvis Bay (Bird Sanctuary), Namibia.

RESULTS

Euryomma peregrinum (MEIGEN, 1826) (FIG. 2)

DISTRIBUTION: *Euryomma peregrinum* is a cosmopolitan species (PONT 1977) that has been recorded in the Holarctic, Neotropic, Afrotropical, Australian and Oriental regions.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION: Palearctic region: Europe, Azores, Canary Is., Madeira (BECKER 1908; CHILLCOTT 1961; PONT 1986; SÉGUY 1923; STEIN 1908); Nearctic region: (CHILLCOTT 1958; GRISALES *et AL.* 2012; PONT 1986), South Greenland (CHILLCOTT 1961); Neotropical

region: Argentina (ABALLAY *et al.* 2012); Brazil (ALMEIDA *et al.* 1984; CARVALHO *et al.* 2002; WENDT & CARVALHO 2007); Peru, Chile (CHILLCOTT 1961; HENNIG 1955; STEIN 1911); Guadalupe Is. (ARNAUD 1959); Easter Is. (CAMPOS & PEÑA 1973); Alejandro Selkirk Is. (HENNIG 1955); Australasian and Oriental regions: (CHILLCOTT 1961; LEE *et al.* 1956; PONT 1977), Hawaii (BRYAN 1934); Afrotropical region: Amsterdam Is. (SÉGUY 1960); St Helena Is. (PONT 1980).

FIG. 2. *Euryomma peregrinum* (MEIGEN, 1826), female collected in Walvis Bay in 2018, lateral view.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: Walvis Bay, KEIB Namibia Exp, leg., 19 XI 2018, 1♀.

Examination of material in the NHM collection revealed 110 individuals agreeing with the collected material (label data are provided verbatim) from Namibia:

- 1 ♂, 1 ♀: „Sainte-Helene: Est / Basse Fisher’s Valley / Irrigations, 1000 ft / 14-19.XII.1965”; “COLL MUS TERVUREN / Mission Zool, Ste-Helene / (P. BASILEWSKY, P. L. G. / Benoit et N. Leleup)”; “*Euryomma peregrinum* / A.C. PONT det. 1968”;
- 32 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀: “SOUTH WEST AFRICA (W24) / Walvis Bay / 25-26.I.1972 / Pool edge in dunes.”; “Southern Africa Exp. / B M. 1972 – 1”;
- 1 ♂: “general / sweeping”; “S. W. AFRICA (17) / Swakopmund / 19-20.I.1972”; “Southern African Exp / B.M. 1972 – 1”;

- 28 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀: “general / sweeping”; “S. W. AFRICA (25) / Swakopmund / 26-30.I.1972”; “Southern African Exp / B.M. 1972 – 1”;
- 12 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀: “general / sweeping”; “S. W. AFRICA (24) / Walvis Bay / 25-26.I.1972”; “Southern African Exp / B.M. 1972 – 1”;
- 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀: “Swept vegetation / around sewage farm / settling tanks”; “S. W. AFRICA (25) / Swakopmund / 26-30.I.1972”; “Southern African Exp / B.M. 1972 – 1”.

DISCUSSION

Knowledge about the biology of *Euryomma* species is still in its infancy (DOMÍNGUEZ & ROIG-JUÑENT 2017; WENDT & CARVALHO 2007). Adults of *E. peregrinum* occur mainly in synanthropic and forest environments. ROZKOŠNY *et AL.* (1997) reported that larvae have been recorded in rotting plant, leaf litter or compost, also in living plants already attacked by other invertebrates. HOLLOWAY (1984) provided a detailed description and identification key for the third instar larvae. *Euryomma peregrinum* is a cosmopolitan species, widespread, but the vast majority of records concern the Neotropical region (CARVALHO *et AL.* 2003; GRISALES *et AL.* 2016), as well as the Holarctic and Australasian regions (CHILLCOTT 1961; PONT 1977, 1991). Despite the fact that *E. peregrinum* is known as a worldwide species, only a few records were hitherto known in Africa: St Helena Island (PONT 1980) and Amsterdam Island (SÉGUY 1960) in the Afrotropical region and Canary Islands and Madeira in the Palaearctic Region (PONT 1986). No other record was found from this region (PONT 1980). In this paper we provide new records of *E. peregrinum* from Namibia. Our recent finding is supported by numerous specimens originating from the same area of West Namibia and deposited in the collection of the NHM. The occurrence of the species in Swakopmund and Walvis Bay results from its transport by commerce, since both are important logistic and touristic places in West Namibia. We here confirm the occurrence of *E. peregrinum* in continental Africa. Further dipterological surveys should reveal wider distribution range of *Euryomma* in Africa. The species is particularly expected to occur in other coastal areas of commercial importance.

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STRESZCZENIE

Euryomma STEIN, 1899 jest drugim, pod względem liczebności gatunków, rodzajem w rodzinie Fanniidae (Diptera). Rodzaj *Euryomma* obejmuje około 16 gatunków odnotowanych przede wszystkim z obszaru Nowego Świata. Muchówki te związane są z obszarami synantropijnymi lub leśnymi, a niektóre z nich mogą pojawiać się na materii organicznej pochodzenia roślinnego lub zwierzęcego. *Euryomma peregrinum* (MEIGEN, 1826) jest jedynym przedstawicielem tego rodzaju charakteryzującym się kosmopolitycznym zasięgiem występowania, wynikającym z rozwoju handlu i różnorodnych środków komunikacji. W trakcie studiowania obszernej literatury tematu nie odnotowaliśmy żadnych oficjalnych zapisów dotyczących występowania tego gatunku w kontynentalnej części Afryki. Artykuł ten stanowi pierwsze oficjalne stwierdzenie występowania *E. peregrinum* w Afryce kontynentalnej, w Namibii.

*** Editorial remarks:**

* Papers of the 35th volume of Dipteron are dedicated to the late AGNIESZKA DRABER-MOŃKO.